

Postoperative Pain Management in Pediatrics in Muhimbili National Hospital, in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania.

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Introduction

Postoperative pain is a common challenge in pediatric surgical care, yet its assessment and management remain difficult due to developmental and communication differences. This study aimed to assess postoperative pain management practices and associated factors among pediatric patients at Muhimbili National Hospital in 2025.

Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional study conducted prospectively among 85 children aged 8 months to 13 years. Pain levels were assessed within the first 48 hours post-surgery using the Modified Objective Pain Scale (MOPS). Additional data were obtained from chart reviews and caregiver questionnaires. Statistical analysis included chi-square testing to determine association.

Results

Moderate to severe pain prevalence was 20%. Preoperative pain, type of surgery, Procedures involving muscle dividing, and postoperative analgesics were significantly associated with higher MOPS scores. Paracetamol and pethidine were the primary analgesics used and were linked to better pain control. Caudal block used primarily in pelvic surgeries was associated with improved pain control.

Conclusion

Findings indicate generally effective pain management but highlight gaps in standardization. Implementing a structured postoperative pain protocol and Improving access to a boarder range of analgesic options may further improve outcomes.

Keywords

Analgesia, MOPS, Pain, Pediatric surgery, Postoperative, Tanzania.